

CUNHA, Leo; MASSARANI, Mariana. **O livro maluco das poções mágicas** [The Crazy Book of Magic Potions]. São Paulo: Brasil, 2019.

REVIEW¹

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The book presents the crazy encounter between Leo Cunha and Mariana Massarani, who team up to tell the story of a bored princess who finds a book full of magic potions. This book contains recipes for making wishes come true, e.g. ‘what if all the sums learnt in school became easy, as if by mathmagic?’. The text written by Leo Cunha offers a riddle with every page and is illustrated with a comical twist by Mariana Massarani. Both are experienced, award-winning Brazilian writers.

Keywords: Magic. Dreams. Imagination.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2020 Bologna. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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